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Dual-Mode, Dual-Polarization Fully-Woven Textile Antenna for Simultaneous Wireless Information and Power Transfer Applications in the 2.4 GHz Band

MIGUEL FERNÁNDEZ¹, CARLOS VÁZQUEZ¹, AND SAMUEL VER HOEYE¹ (Member, IEEE)

Department of Electrical Engineering, University of Oviedo, 33003 Gijón, Spain

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR: M. FERNÁNDEZ (e-mail: fernandezgmiguel@uniovi.es)

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ABSTRACT In this work, a dual-mode, dual-polarization fully-woven textile antenna for simultaneous wireless information and power transfer in the 2.4 GHz band is presented. It is based on a square patch with two independent ports. The first port is implemented with an offset T-match structure, to which a single-diode rectifier is connected. The selected feeding technique allows to obtain complex-conjugate impedance matching with the rectifier and right-hand circular polarization for the wireless power transfer mode. On the other hand, for the information transfer mode, a coaxial probe is used to excite the antenna with left-hand circular polarization, in order to minimize the coupling between both modes. The combination of fully-woven technology with the implementation of the rectifier on a carrier thread provides a high degree of integration and robustness. A prototype was implemented and experimentally characterized, showing good agreement with simulation results. Furthermore, the measured RF-DC conversion efficiency in the wireless power transfer mode is about 50% when the available power at the rectifier input is -10 dBm, which is comparable with the state of the art for textile rectennas.

INDEX TERMS Antennas, rectenna, rectifier, textile technology, wireless power transfer.

I. INTRODUCTION

WEARABLE technologies have attracted a large research effort because of the large number of potential applications in the fields of healthcare and sports [1], among many others, related to the use of sensors to remotely monitor a variety of vital signs.

The use of batteries in wireless wearable devices increases the size and weight of the system, and the periodically required charging cycles, or even battery substitution, negatively impact the user experience. In this context, Energy Harvesting (EH) and Wireless Power Transfer (WPT) have been proposed as viable power supply technologies, specially suited for low-power devices [2]. In energy harvesting, the goal is to harness the power already present in the environment, in the form of radiation originated in non-dedicated sources, such as radio or TV transmitter stations, mobile phone base stations, or Wi-Fi access points [3], [4], [5]. The WPT approach, on the other hand, relies on setting up a

dedicated narrowband RF transmitter as the power source for the system. Thus, since the parameters of the dedicated transmitter are specific, stable and known to the designer, the receiver antenna and rectifier can be optimized for those parameters, leading to higher and more reliable available power levels, as well as better system efficiency values [6].

In addition, the target applications for which WPT technology has been proposed usually require communications capabilities. In the interest of obtaining more compact implementations, an effort has been made in the last few years to integrate both the power transfer and communication capabilities in the same antenna structure, leading to Simultaneous Wireless Information and Power Transfer (SWIPT) antennas [7].

References [8], [9], [10], [11], [12] describe single-band dual-port devices in which the rectifier and the data signal are directly connected to different ports of the antenna [8], [9], [12], or to two isolated ports of an hybrid

52 coupler [10], [11], achieving dual-linear or dual-circular
 53 polarization for the two working modes. Dual-band SWIPT
 54 antennas have also been presented [13], [14], [15], in which
 55 the power transfer and the data link are performed at different
 56 frequency bands, achieving large isolation between them, but
 57 requiring more complex structures. With the exception of the
 58 textile devices reported in [12] and [15], all the previously
 59 cited works describe antennas implemented in conventional
 60 rigid RF substrates, requiring, in general, complex and/or
 61 multilayer structures. Furthermore, the connection to the
 62 rectifier is made through large-size impedance matching
 63 networks, which make them unsuitable for wearable devices.

64 Textile antennas are good candidates for the implementa-
 65 tion of wearable devices due to their inherent flexibility
 66 and ease of integration in fabric. Different implementation
 67 technologies based on stacking several shaped conductive
 68 and dielectric fabric pieces [12], [15], embroidering with
 69 conductive thread on a fabric sheet [16], [17], or screen-
 70 printing on a cotton fabric [18], have been proposed.
 71 Although these solutions achieve good performance, the
 72 use of lumped electronic components soldered to textile
 73 pads compromises robustness and integration capability in
 74 wearable applications.

75 A different approach based on the use of fully-woven
 76 structures has also been reported. The main advantages
 77 of this technology are the improved robustness and ease
 78 of integration with larger elements, the design flexibility,
 79 and the capability of large-scale production using processes
 80 from the textile industry. This technology has been applied to
 81 the development of microwave waveguides [19], frequency
 82 selective surfaces [20], [21], and antennas [22], [23], as well
 83 as textile LF [24] and UHF [25] RFID tags, and recten-
 84 nas [26]. In these systems, the electronic components are first
 85 mounted on a carrier thread and then woven with the rest of
 86 the structure. Thus, they are inseparably integrated into the
 87 textile material, which preserves its inherent properties, such
 88 as robustness, flexibility and scalability to mass production.

89 In this work, a fully-woven dual-mode, dual-polarization
 90 textile antenna for SWIPT applications in the 2.4 GHz
 91 band is presented. The layout of the antenna is based
 92 on a nearly square patch with two independent ports to
 93 separately connect the rectifier and the data signal. The two
 94 working modes operate with orthogonal circular polarization,
 95 to minimize the negative impact of polarization mismatch
 96 between the transmitter and the receiver antennas, and to
 97 minimize the coupling between the two signals. Furthermore,
 98 the obtained layout is suitable for fabrication in fully-woven
 99 technology and, when combined with the technique described
 100 in [25] and [26] to mount the rectifier, it provides a large
 101 degree of integration and robustness.

102 The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II
 103 describes the topology and the woven structure of the
 104 proposed antenna. In Section III, the design process of the
 105 antenna and the rectifier is presented. Section IV provides
 106 some details about the implementation. The experimental
 107 results are presented and analyzed in Section V.

FIGURE 1. a) Topology of the proposed SWIPT antenna and schematic diagram of the rectifier. b) Fully-woven structure of the antenna.

II. ANTENNA OVERVIEW

A. TOPOLOGY

Fig. 1 a) schematizes the topology of the proposed antenna. It is based on a nearly square patch with two independent ports to connect the rectifier and the data signal. The rectifier is connected through an offset T-match structure, which provides simultaneous complex conjugate impedance matching to the rectifier and right-hand circular polarization (RHCP). On the other hand, the data signal is connected to the antenna using a 50Ω coaxial probe, whose location is selected to provide left-hand circular polarization (LHCP).

A patch antenna was selected as the basis for the design because it provides some key characteristics for the considered development. First, it presents a low-profile, three-layer structure, and a geometrically simple layout which can be easily integrated with the T-match feeding network, since all the elements are on the same plane. Thus, a compact layout compatible with the fully-woven textile technology is obtained. Furthermore, the inherent ground plane of the antenna isolates it from the underlying objects, limiting their impact on the antenna performance, which is a very valuable characteristics when considering wearable applications.

The topology of the rectifier is shown in the top part of Fig. 1 a). It includes a single Schottky diode and a shunt capacitor to short circuit the RF signal at the diode output. A series inductor is added to partially compensate for the high capacitive part of the rectifier input impedance Z_r . The circuit is mounted on a carrier thread and then woven with the

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rest of the textile structure of the antenna, providing a high degree of integration and robustness, since the connection between the rectifier and the antenna is made through the multiple contact points generated between the woven thread filaments.

B. FULLY-WOVEN STRUCTURE

The woven structure of the antenna is schematized in Fig. 1 b). The multilayer fabric is composed of two conductive layers separated by a dielectric layer. The layout of the antenna is patterned on one of the conductive layers, while the other works as the ground plane. It is intended to be manufactured in a single step, using an industrial loom. Thus, the structure is based on a combination of warp and weft threads, which are perpendicular between them. The fabric density is conditioned by the epi and ppi loom parameters, which indicate the number of warp and weft threads per inch. In this case, epi = 100, and ppi = 100.

The conductive layers are woven with *ELITEX 117/f17 2ply* threads, formed by two twisted yarns, each one with 17 filaments. The filaments are extruded from polyamide, with relative dielectric constant $\epsilon_r = 2.6$, and they are silver coated with 1 μm thickness, providing a 70 Ω/m linear resistance. Their linear density is 234 dtex, which indicates the weight, in grams, of a 10 km length of thread. On the other hand, the dielectric layer is woven with threads composed of two twisted yarns, extruded from polyester, with relative dielectric permittivity $\epsilon_r = 4.1$, and 334 dtex linear density.

Finally, dielectric binder threads, identical to those employed to weaving the dielectric layer, are used to hold the conductive and dielectric layers together, obtaining a unique multilayer fabric. This fully-woven approach provides improved robustness when compared with nonwoven technologies, in which several independent fabric sheets have to be separately handled and attached together. Furthermore, the proposed structure can be manufactured in a single step using an industrial loom, enabling large-scale production.

III. DESIGN AND OPTIMIZATION

The design process comprises two main steps. Initially, only the patch antenna with the WPT port is considered. In order to maximize the power transfer between the antenna and the rectifier, they were jointly optimized. First, the rectifier was designed and its input impedance Z_r was calculated, using the Harmonic Balance (HB) technique implemented in the *Keysight ADS* commercial package. Then, the antenna was optimized, using *Ansys HFSS*, to achieve an input impedance at the WPT port Z_{WPT} as close as possible to Z_r^* . At the second design step, the 50 Ω port for the data signal was added, and the whole system was re-optimized to simultaneously satisfy all the design requirements.

A. RECTIFIER

The rectifier topology, shown in Fig. 1 a), is similar to that used in [26], and it was selected to obtain a layout

simple enough to be integrated into the woven antenna as described in [25] and [26]. It is composed of a single *Infineon BAT 15-04W* Schottky diode and a shunt capacitor $C = 1$ nF to short circuit the RF signal at the diode output, maximizing the RF current. An input series inductor $L = 2.4$ nH is added to partially compensate for the large capacitive input impedance of the whole device, thus simplifying the impedance matching with the antenna. A resistor $R = 5.1$ k Ω is placed at the rectifier output to simulate the rectifier load. Its value was selected to maximize the RF-DC conversion efficiency [26]. The output DC voltage V_{DC} is taken at the resistor terminals.

The circuit was optimized to maximize the RF-DC conversion efficiency, considering an input RF signal generated by a dedicated WPT source with frequency $f_{RF} = 2.4$ GHz, and available power $P_{RF} = -10$ dBm at the rectifier input, which is a realistic value when taking into account the EIRP limitations for indoor transmitters and the free space propagation losses. Nonlinear simulations based on the HB technique were used to calculate the rectifier input impedance Z_r , the RF-DC conversion efficiency, and the output DC voltage V_{DC} and Power P_{DC} , when the circuit operates under the described conditions. The obtained values are $Z_r = 16 - j138$ Ω , about 60% RF-DC conversion efficiency, $V_{DC} \approx 0.5$ V, and $P_{DC} \approx 60$ μW .

From the obtained values, it is expected that the RF-DC conversion efficiency of the whole antenna-rectifier system reaches its maximum value, about 60% according to the rectifier performance, when the input impedance of the antenna at the WPT port is $Z_{WPT} = Z_r^* = 16 + j138$ Ω . However, since the dimensional accuracy that can be achieved when implementing woven textile devices is not as high as in conventional PCB technologies, the value of Z_{WPT} obtained in practice could be slightly deviated from the optimum Z_r^* . Moreover, because of the flexibility of textile devices, they will suffer deformations under real usage conditions, which could modify the antenna input impedance. Fig. 2 shows the evolution of the RF-DC conversion efficiency with the WPT port impedance Z_{WPT} . As expected, the maximum 60% efficiency value is obtained when $Z_{WPT} = Z_r^* = 16 + j138$ Ω , whereas it is larger than 50% for a 20 Ω variation about the optimum point, both in the real R_{WPT} and the imaginary X_{WPT} parts of the antenna input impedance. The output DC voltage values V_{DC} as a function of the WPT port impedance are represented in Fig. 3.

B. ANTENNA

1) EM MODELING OF WOVEN STRUCTURES

Without any simplification, the accurate EM modeling of woven structures is a demanding task [25], because of their inherent geometrical complexity, as schematized in Fig. 1 b), and the fact that each thread is, in general, composed of several filaments. To overcome that issue, some strategies were proposed to reduce the model complexity while preserving its accuracy [27], [28].

FIGURE 2. Variation of the RF-DC conversion efficiency with the impedance of the antenna WPT port Z_{WPT} , evaluated at $f_{RF} = 2.4$ GHz. The available power at the rectifier input is $P_{RF} = -10$ dBm.

FIGURE 3. Variation of the rectifier output DC voltage V_{DC} , in V, with the impedance of the antenna WPT port, evaluated at $f_{RF} = 2.4$ GHz. The available power at the rectifier input is $P_{RF} = -10$ dBm.

245 The dielectric woven layers can be modeled as equivalent
 246 homogeneous layers, with the same thickness h_{diel} and an
 247 equivalent dielectric permittivity $\epsilon_{r,eq}$, which is reduced with
 248 respect to the value of the polyester from which the threads
 249 are extruded. This is due to the air gaps contained in the
 250 woven structure, which depends on the epi and ppi loom
 251 parameters. The value used here, $\epsilon_{r,eq} \approx 1.8$, was estimated
 252 from the experimental characterization of a transmission
 253 line and a resonator implemented with the same fabric
 254 structure as the antenna. In this way, the obtained value
 255 takes into account all the material parameters and characteristics,
 256 including the effect of the binder threads. The loss tangent
 257 was also estimated, obtaining $\tan \delta \approx 0.04$.

258 Considering the conductive layers, since a large number
 259 of contacts between warp and weft conductive threads is
 260 generated at the weaving stage, the current can flow in any
 261 direction. In addition, the skin depth on the silver coating at
 262 the 2.4 GHz working frequency is about $1.3 \mu\text{m}$, larger than
 263 the $1 \mu\text{m}$ coating thickness. Thus, the conductive woven
 264 layers can also be modeled as homogeneous conductive

FIGURE 4. Evolution of the antenna impedance at the WPT port, Z_{WPT} , with the displacement of the T-match structure. Continuous trace: Real part. Dashed trace: Imaginary part.

265 sheets, with the same thickness as the silver coating of the
 266 threads, $h_{cond} = 1 \mu\text{m}$, and an equivalent conductivity $\sigma_{eq} =$
 267 6.3×10^7 S/m, similar to that of the filament silver coating.

2) WPT MODE

268 The antenna design is based on a nearly square patch sized to
 269 work around 2.4 GHz. The main goal at this step is to adjust
 270 the impedance at the WPT port to match that of the rectifier,
 271 $Z_{WPT} = Z_r^*$, to maximize the power transfer between them.
 272 Thus, the port to connect the rectifier is implemented as a
 273 T-match structure, which allows a relatively easy control
 274 of both the real and the imaginary parts of the input
 275 impedance Z_{WPT} , while providing a high and controllable
 276 inductive component, which is necessary to compensate for
 277 the capacitive part of Z_r . Furthermore, to obtain circular
 278 polarization, the T-match structure is connected to the patch
 279 edge close to one of the corners, as schematized in Fig. 1a).

280 The dependence of Z_{WPT} with the T-match network
 281 geometrical parameters is determined through a parametric
 282 analysis. The width of the structure arms is kept constant
 283 at $w = 2$ mm, whereas the port width is set to $p = 6$ mm
 284 to have space for the rectifier layout. The T-match network
 285 provides an input impedance with a low real part R_{WPT} and
 286 a large inductive imaginary part X_{WPT} . As described in [26],
 287 both the real and the imaginary parts of Z_{WPT} increase with
 288 the total length of the loop, i. e., when increasing g and/or
 289 l . On the other hand, the value of R_{WPT} increases with the
 290 value of g , while it is weakly dependent on l . The effect of
 291 moving the feeding point from the edge center on Z_{WPT} is
 292 shown in Fig. 4. Note that the real and the imaginary parts of
 293 Z_{WPT} are modified, but they can still be controlled by
 294 adjusting l and g . Table 1 displays the values of the
 295 optimized parameters. The impedance at the WPT port,
 296 evaluated at $f_{RF} = 2.4$ GHz is $Z_{WPT} = 16 + j138 \Omega$, which
 297 provides complex conjugate matching to the rectifier.
 298

299 Fig. 5 represents the normalized RHCP and LHCP
 300 components of the antenna radiation pattern, evaluated in the
 301 $\varphi = 0^\circ$ plane, obtained when exciting the WPT port. The
 302 radiation pattern exhibits the expected angular variation for
 303 a patch antenna, with a maximum simulated gain slightly

TABLE 1. Optimized parameters.

Parameter	L_p	l	g	d	d_x	d_y
Value (mm)	42.2	11.2	4.8	12	2.6	19.8

FIGURE 6. Evolution of the axial ratio, evaluated at the $\theta = 0^\circ$ direction, with the working frequency. Continuous line: Isolated antenna. Dashed line: Effect of the human body proximity. Inset: Multilayer human tissue model.

larger than 0 dB, because of the relatively large value of the textile substrate $\tan \delta$. The variation of the axial ratio with the working frequency, evaluated at the maximum gain direction, $\theta = 0^\circ$, is represented in Fig. 6, showing a value under 3 dB in the 2.37 – 2.43 GHz range. In the same frequency range, the input impedance of the WPT port varies from $14.5 + j132 \Omega$ to $22.5 + j143 \Omega$, which, taking into account the results presented in Fig. 2, should provide a RF-DC conversion efficiency higher than 55%.

3) DATA LINK PORT

After optimizing the antenna for the WPT mode, a coaxial probe port for the connection of the data signal is added. The port is located close to the opposite edge at which the WPT port is connected, slightly deviated from the x-axis

FIGURE 7. $S_{data,data}$: Input reflection coefficient evaluated at the data port. $S_{WPT,data}$: Coupling coefficient between the WPT and the data port. Continuous line: Isolated antenna. Dashed line: Effect of the human body proximity.

symmetry line, as schematized in Fig. 1 a). This location was selected to simultaneously obtain good 50Ω impedance matching and LH circular polarization, taking advantage of the perturbation on the patch shape created by the T-match structure.

The simulated impedance matching at the data port, $S_{data,data}$, and the coupling between the WPT and the data ports, $S_{WPT,data}$, are represented in Fig. 7, showing acceptable performance. On the other hand, Figs. 5 and 6 represent the LHCP and RHCP components of the radiation pattern, and the frequency dependence of the axial ratio, evaluated when the data port is excited. Note that a high isolation between the WPT and the data transfer modes is achieved because their center frequencies are 50 MHz apart, and both modes operate with orthogonal circular polarizations.

C. EFFECT OF HUMAN BODY PROXIMITY

To numerically analyze the effect of the human body proximity on the antenna performance, it was placed over a multilayer human tissue model, composed of skin, fat, muscle and bone [29], as schematized in the inset of Fig. 6. The electrical parameters and the thickness of each layer are shown in Table 2, and the side length was set to 200 mm, slightly smaller than 2λ at 2.4 GHz, in order to ensure accurate results. A 2 mm thickness additional layer between the antenna and the human tissue model, with the same electrical parameters as those used for the dielectric layer of the antenna, was added to simulate the effect of a garment between the antenna and the body.

The impact of the human body proximity on the input impedance at the WPT port, Z_{WPT} , is represented in Fig. 4, showing a variation smaller than 2Ω , with respect to the case in which the isolated antenna is considered. Thus, the effect on the RF-DC conversion efficiency is expected to be negligible. Regarding the data transfer mode, the relevant S parameters are compared in Fig. 7. Finally, the influence of human body proximity on the polarization

TABLE 2. Parameters of each tissue layer.

	Skin	Fat	Muscle	Bone
ϵ_r	37	5.2	51.5	10.8
σ (S/m)	2.02	0.16	2.56	0.61
Thickness (mm)	3	7	20	10

FIGURE 8. Manufactured antenna mounted on an anechoic chamber.

355 properties of the antenna is displayed in Fig. 6. Note
 356 that, from all the previously presented results and, as
 357 expected for a radiating structure with a large enough ground
 358 plane, the effect of the human body proximity on the
 359 antenna performance is very small. Furthermore, it can be
 360 derived that the backward radiation level is very reduced,
 361 which is also a very valuable characteristic for a wearable
 362 application.

363 IV. IMPLEMENTATION

364 A. ANTENNA

365 A multilayer fabric piece composed of an inner dielectric
 366 part between two conductive sheets, as schematized in
 367 Fig. 1 b), was used as substrate for the antenna. Its layout,
 368 including the patch and the T-match port to connect the
 369 rectifier, was structured on the top conductive layer by laser
 370 cutting the conductive threads and removing the excess part.
 371 Although the cutting accuracy of the laser process can be
 372 considered ideal at the 2.4 GHz working frequency, the
 373 achieved geometrical accuracy is limited by the diameter
 374 of the conductive threads, since that value imposes the
 375 minimum strip width which can be removed.

376 To test the performance of the data link mode, a coaxial
 377 connector was attached to the antenna, and the inner and
 378 the outer conductors were connected to the top and bottom
 379 conductive layers, respectively, with conductive epoxy solder
 380 paste. Note that, in a final application, this coaxial connector
 381 is not strictly necessary, since the antenna could be directly
 382 connected to the data signal source, ideally located under
 383 the ground plane, through a conductive thread. Figure 8.
 384 shows a picture of the manufactured prototype in an anechoic
 385 chamber.

FIGURE 9. a) Measured output DC voltage V_{DC} for different available power levels at the rectifier input. b) Evaluated output DC power P_{DC} .

FIGURE 10. Measured RF-DC conversion efficiency for different available power levels at the rectifier input. For the sake of the representation clarity, only the case in which the antenna is bent along the x axis is considered.

386 B. RECTIFIER

387 The rectifier was integrated into the woven structure as
 388 described in [25], [26] in order to obtain a large degree
 389 of integration and robustness. First, the rectifier was
 390 implemented on a 50 μm thickness flexible polyimide strip,
 391 with dielectric permittivity $\epsilon_r = 3$, on which the pads for
 392 the diode and the other discrete components, and the contact
 393 areas with the fabric, were patterned using silver based
 394 conductive ink. Next, the strip was glued to a carrier thread
 395 and, finally, the carrier thread was integrated with the antenna
 396 by weaving it with the textile structure at the WPT port.

397 The proposed integration technique presents two main
 398 advantages. On the one hand, the circuit is first mounted on a
 399 carrier thread, which can be handled as a conventional thread
 400 at the weaving stage, enabling large-scale production. On
 401 the other hand, the electrical contact between the terminals
 402 of the rectifier and the antenna is made through the large
 403 number of contact points created when weaving the carrier
 404 thread with the rest of the structure. Thus, the robustness

FIGURE 11. Evolution of the measured output DC power P_{DC} with the φ rotation angle.

FIGURE 12. Measured reflection coefficient at the data link port, together with simulation results. Inset: Picture of the antenna placed over a human torso.

405 is improved, since no soldered joints with fabric parts are
406 required.

407 V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

408 A. WPT MODE

409 1) MEASUREMENT SETUP

410 To characterize the performance of the proposed antenna
411 working in the WPT mode, with the data link port loaded
412 with a matched load, a WPT transmitter composed of an
413 RF signal source with frequency $f_{RF} = 2.4$ GHz, and a
414 linearly polarized patch antenna with gain $G_{TX} \approx 4$ dB, was
415 used [26]. The power of the signal source was set to 23
416 dBm in order not to exceed the European EIRP limit for
417 indoor ISM transmitters. The nominal distance between the
418 transmitter and the receiver antennas was set to $d = 0.5$
419 m, which corresponds to a free-space propagation loss of
420 about 34 dB at $f_{RF} = 2.4$ GHz. Furthermore, an additional
421 3 dB polarization mismatch loss factor between the linearly
422 polarized transmitter antenna and the circularly polarized
423 receiver one has to be considered. Thus, the available power
424 at the rectifier input is $P_{RF} \approx -10$ dBm.

425 At the receiver side, a multimeter was used to measure
426 the rectified DC voltage V_{DC} at the terminals of the

FIGURE 13. Measured LHCP and RHCP components at 2.45 GHz. Blue trace: undeformed antenna. Red trace: antenna bent along the x axis. Black trace: antenna bent along y axis.

FIGURE 14. Measured evolution of the axial ratio, evaluated at the maximum radiation direction $\theta = 0^\circ$, with the working frequency.

427 resistor, from which the rectified DC power P_{DC} can
428 be calculated. Furthermore, other distances between the
429 transmitter and the receiver were considered, in order to
430 evaluate the performance of the system for different available
431 power levels at the rectifier input. The measurements were
432 performed in a non anechoic laboratory environment, to
433 obtain results as close as possible to a real use scenario.

434 2) RESULTS

435 The evolution of the measured output DC voltage and power
436 with frequency is represented in Fig. 9. As expected, the
437 largest values are obtained around 2.4 GHz because the T-
438 match impedance matching network provides the optimum
439 performance at that frequency. Note that the variation with
440 frequency is smooth because, as represented in Fig. 3,
441 relatively large changes in the antenna input impedance Z_{WPT}
442 cause small efficiency variations.

443 To analyze the impact of possible deformations on the
444 rectenna performance, it was bent along the x and the y axis
445 (see Fig. 1) with a radius $r = 20$ cm, as schematized in
446 the inset of Fig. 11. The measured results are represented in

TABLE 3. Comparison with the state of the art.

Ref.	WPT/Comm. freq. (GHz)	Isolation (dB)	Polarization	Power (dBm)	Efficiency (%)	Modes	Technology
[8]	2.4	13	Circular	0	45	SWIPT	Rigid PCB
[9]	5.8/6.1	25	Dual Linear	14	65	SWIPT	Rigid PCB
[10]	5.7/5.8	15	D. Linear/D. Circular	0.5	51	SWIPT/Rectenna	Rigid PCB
[11]	4.2-6.7	-	D. Linear/D. Circular	10	71	SWIPT/Rectenna	Rigid PCB
[13]	5.8/2.4	-	Dual Circular	12	63	Dual-band SWIPT	Rigid PCB
[14]	5/5.7	12	Linear	5	51	Dual-band SWIPT	Rigid PCB
[12]	2.4	16	Dual Linear	2	74	SWIPT	Nonwoven textile
[15]	0.83/2.4	-	Linear	-10	62	Dual-band SWIPT	Nonwoven textile
This work	2.4	20	Dual Circular	-10	50	SWIPT	Fully-woven textile

Fig. 9, showing small variations with respect to the undeformed antenna. Furthermore, to evaluate the performance of the antenna in a scenario close to a real wearable application, it was placed over the torso of a volunteer, as shown in the inset of Fig. 12, using a 90° bent coaxial adapter to connect the coaxial cable required for the characterization of the data link mode. Due to the inherent ground plane of the selected radiating structure, the effect of the underneath body does not have appreciable influence on the measured V_{DC} and P_{DC} values.

Figure 10 shows the evolution of the measured RF-DC conversion efficiency with the working frequency for different values of available power at the rectifier input. The maximum value is about 50%, which is aligned with the state of the art for textile rectennas working at the 2.4 GHz frequency band. Furthermore, the measured maximum efficiency is similar in all the scenarios in which the available power at the rectifier input is larger than -10 dBm, and it is slightly reduced in the case in which the rectifier is driven with -12 dBm. Finally, note that bending the antenna or placing it over a human torso has a low impact on the conversion efficiency.

To analyze the polarization characteristics of the rectenna, it was rotated around the z axis from 0° to 90°, in 15° steps, measuring the values of the output V_{DC} and P_{DC} for each rotation angle. The normalized output DC power P_{DC} is represented in Fig. 11. Considering the undeformed antenna, the variation of the obtained DC power is smaller than 3 dB, showing the antenna exhibits circular polarization at the WPT mode. On the other hand, when deforming the antenna, the power variation increases, but it is smaller than 3.5 dB.

B. DATA LINK MODE

First, the reflection coefficient at the data link port was evaluated. A previously calibrated Vector Network Analyzer (VNA) was connected to the data link port, using the coaxial connector shown in Fig. 8, through a short length coaxial cable. The result is represented in Fig. 12, together with the simulation data, showing good agreement between them, and good stability against antenna deformations. The effect

of placing the antenna near to the human body was also evaluated as described in the previous point. Note that, because of the presence of a ground plane, the antenna performance remains practically unchanged.

The radiation pattern characteristics, including the gain and the axial ratio, were evaluated in an anechoic chamber using conventional antenna measurement techniques. Fig. 13 represents the normalized measured LHCP and RHCP components, at 2.45 GHz, showing the expected angular properties for a patch antenna, and that the antenna working at the data transfer mode exhibits LH circular polarization. On the other hand, bending the antenna along the two main axes has low impact on the directional properties of the radiation pattern, but increases the level of the cross-polar components. The measured gain is about 0 dB.

Fig. 14 represents the measured evolution of the axial ratio, evaluated at the maximum radiation direction $\theta = 0^\circ$ with frequency, showing good agreement with simulation data for the undeformed antenna. When the antenna is deformed, the minimum value of the axial ratio is slightly shifted in frequency, but the obtained value at 2.45 GHz is still under 3 dB.

C. COMPARISON WITH THE STATE OF THE ART

Table 3 summarizes the performance comparison between the prototype presented in this work and recently reported antennas for SWIPT applications. With the exception of [12] and [15], in which nonwoven textile devices are described, all the works report antennas implemented in conventional rigid substrates, which makes them unsuitable for their use in wearables.

The compared antennas are based on different SWIPT approaches. In [13], [14], [15], the WPT and the information transmission are performed at different frequency bands, which simplifies the design of each channel but requires more complex radiating structures, which can be considered as two antennas with some EM interaction between them. On the other hand, the rest of the works describe single-band SWIPT antennas which separate the WPT and the communication channels by using two orthogonal linear polarizations. Moreover, in the case of [10] and [11], the

SWIPT antennas can work either with linear or circular polarization, depending on the selected port configuration.

Regarding the RF-DC conversion efficiency, most of the previously published works report values slightly higher than those presented here, but they are achieved with available power values at the rectifier input in the 5-14 dBm which, taking into account the transmitter power limitations and the propagation losses, do not correspond with a realistic scenario. In the case of [15], a 62% efficiency achieved with -10 dBm available power at the rectifier input is reported. However, it should be considered that the rectifier works in the 800 MHz band, in which the performance of the diodes is considerably better than in the 2.4 and 5 GHz frequency bands.

In this work, the first fully-woven single-band SWIPT antenna able to separate the WPT and the information signals by using two orthogonal circular polarizations is presented, showing a performance comparable to the state of the art for textile and conventional PCB rectennas. Thus, the work demonstrates that fully-woven technology is a suitable approach for the development of wearable devices, since it is able to combine good electrical performance with the advantages of textile materials.

VI. CONCLUSION

A dual-mode dual-polarization fully-woven textile antenna for SWIPT applications in the 2.4 GHz band was presented. It is based on a square patch with two independent ports. The first one is intended to connect a single Schottky diode rectifier. It consists of a T-match structure which allows the control of the port impedance to provide complex conjugate impedance matching to the rectifier. Its off-center location generates RH circular polarization when the antenna operates in the WPT mode. The second port is a 50 Ω coaxial probe to which the data signal will be delivered. Its location was carefully selected to obtain acceptable impedance matching and to excite the radiating element with LH circular polarization. Since the two modes operate with orthogonal polarization and at slightly different frequencies, a large isolation between the WPT and the data signals is achieved. The described combination of design techniques leads to a layout compatible with the fully-woven implementation. Furthermore, by mounting the rectifier on a carrier thread, which is subsequently woven into the textile structure, improved robustness and a high degree of integration are achieved.

A prototype was implemented and experimentally characterized. Considering the WPT working mode, the measured RF-DC conversion efficiency is about 50% when the rectifier input available power is -10 dBm, which is a realistic value, considering a transmitter with a 27 dBm EIRP, which fulfils European regulations, placed at a distance of 0.5 m from the antenna. The measured efficiency value is close to the simulations, and comparable to the most-recently reported values for textile nonwoven implementations. Regarding the data transfer mode, the measured impedance matching and

the radiation pattern characteristics are in good agreement with the simulation data. Thus, the design and implementation strategies are validated, and it is shown that the inherent advantages of fully-woven technology, i.e., flexibility, robustness, ease of integration with larger textile elements, and the possibility of industrial large-scale production, can be exploited to design wearable devices, representing a feasible alternative to other nonwoven technologies.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A. Kiourti et al., "Next-generation healthcare: Enabling technologies for emerging bioelectromagnetics applications," *IEEE Open J. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 3, pp. 363–390, 2022, doi: [10.1109/OJAP.2022.3162110](https://doi.org/10.1109/OJAP.2022.3162110).
- [2] M. Wagih et al., "Microwave-enabled wearables: Underpinning technologies, integration platforms, and next-generation roadmap," *IEEE J. Microw.*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 193–226, Jan. 2023, doi: [10.1109/JMW.2022.3223254](https://doi.org/10.1109/JMW.2022.3223254).
- [3] S. Kim et al., "Ambient RF energy-harvesting technologies for self-sustainable standalone wireless sensor platforms," *Proc. IEEE*, vol. 102, no. 11, pp. 1649–1666, Nov. 2014, doi: [10.1109/JPROC.2014.2357031](https://doi.org/10.1109/JPROC.2014.2357031).
- [4] M. Piñuela, P. D. Mitcheson, and S. Lucyszyn, "Ambient RF energy harvesting in urban and semi-urban environments," *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Tech.*, vol. 61, no. 7, pp. 2715–2726, Jul. 2013, doi: [10.1109/TMTT.2013.2262687](https://doi.org/10.1109/TMTT.2013.2262687).
- [5] S. Saab, N. Kouzayha, A. Eid, A. A. Benbuk, J. Costantine, and Z. Dawy, "Recycling ambient Wi-Fi signals for low energy wake-up of wireless sensors," *IEEE Sens. Lett.*, vol. 4, no. 10, pp. 1–4, Oct. 2020, doi: [10.1109/LSSENS.2020.3026236](https://doi.org/10.1109/LSSENS.2020.3026236).
- [6] A. J. Williams, M. F. Torquato, I. M. Cameron, A. A. Fahmy, and J. Sienz, "Survey of energy harvesting technologies for wireless sensor networks," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 77493–77510, 2021, doi: [10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3083697](https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3083697).
- [7] B. Clerckx, R. Zhang, R. Schober, D. W. Kwan Ng, D. I. Kim, and H. V. Poor, "Fundamentals of wireless information and power transfer: from RF energy harvester models to signal and system designs," *IEEE J. Sel. Areas Commun.*, vol. 37, no. 1, pp. 4–33, Jan. 2019, doi: [10.1109/JSAC.2018.2872615](https://doi.org/10.1109/JSAC.2018.2872615).
- [8] J. Bitto, R. Bahr, J. G. Hester, S. A. Nurooze, A. Georgiadis, and M. M. Tentzeris, "A novel solar and electromagnetic energy harvesting system with a 3-D printed package for energy efficient Internet-of-Things wireless sensors," *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Tech.*, vol. 65, no. 5, pp. 1831–1842, May 2017, doi: [10.1109/TMTT.2017.2660487](https://doi.org/10.1109/TMTT.2017.2660487).
- [9] X.-X. Yang, C. Jiang, A. Z. Elsherbeni, F. Yang, and Y.-Q. Wang, "A novel compact printed rectenna for data communication systems," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 61, no. 5, pp. 2532–2539, May 2013, doi: [10.1109/TAP.2013.2244550](https://doi.org/10.1109/TAP.2013.2244550).
- [10] P. Lu, C. Song, and K. M. Huang, "A two-port multipolarization rectenna with orthogonal hybrid coupler for simultaneous wireless information and power transfer (SWIPT)," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 68, no. 10, pp. 6893–6905, Oct. 2020, doi: [10.1109/TAP.2020.2993096](https://doi.org/10.1109/TAP.2020.2993096).
- [11] C. Cao, X. Zhang, C. Song, A. Georgiadis, and G. Goussetis, "A highly integrated multipolarization wideband rectenna for simultaneous wireless information and power transfer," *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 71, no. 10, pp. 7980–7991, Oct. 2023, doi: [10.1109/TAP.2023.3306182](https://doi.org/10.1109/TAP.2023.3306182).
- [12] M. Wagih, G. S. Hilton, A. S. Weddell, and S. Beeby, "Dual-polarized wearable antenna/rectenna for full-duplex and MIMO simultaneous wireless information and power transfer (SWIPT)," *IEEE Open J. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 2, pp. 844–857, 2021, doi: [10.1109/OJAP.2021.3098939](https://doi.org/10.1109/OJAP.2021.3098939).

648 [13] J.-H. Ou et al., “Highly-isolated RF power and information receiving
649 system based on dual-band dual-circular-polarized shared-aperture
650 antenna,” *IEEE Trans. Circuits Syst. I, Reg. Papers*, vol. 69, no. 8,
651 pp. 3093–3101, Aug. 2022, doi: [10.1109/TCSI.2022.3173688](https://doi.org/10.1109/TCSI.2022.3173688).

652 [14] P. Lu, X.-S. Yang, and B.-Z. Wang, “A two-port frequency recon-
653 figurable rectenna for microwave power transmission and data
654 communication,” *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 65, no. 12,
655 pp. 6976–6985, Dec. 2017, doi: [10.1109/TAP.2017.2766450](https://doi.org/10.1109/TAP.2017.2766450).

656 [15] M. Wagih, G. S. Hilton, A. S. Weddell, and S. Beeby, “Dual-band dual-
657 mode textile antenna/rectenna for simultaneous wireless information
658 and power transfer (SWIPT),” *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 69,
659 no. 10, pp. 6322–6332, Oct. 2021, doi: [10.1109/TAP.2021.3070230](https://doi.org/10.1109/TAP.2021.3070230).

660 [16] C.-X. Mao, D. Vital, D. H. Werner, Y. Wu, and S. Bhardwaj,
661 “Dual-polarized embroidered textile armband antenna array with omni-
662 directional radiation for on/off-body wearable applications,” *IEEE*
663 *Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 68, no. 4, pp. 2575–2584, Apr. 2020,
664 doi: [10.1109/TAP.2019.2951517](https://doi.org/10.1109/TAP.2019.2951517).

665 [17] D. Vital, S. Bhardwaj, and J. L. Volakis, “Textile-based large
666 area RF-power harvesting system for wearable applications,” *IEEE*
667 *Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 68, no. 3, pp. 2323–2431, Mar. 2020,
668 doi: [10.1109/TAP.2019.2948521](https://doi.org/10.1109/TAP.2019.2948521).

669 [18] J. A. Estrada et al., “RF-harvesting tightly coupled rectenna
670 array tee-shirt with greater than octave bandwidth,” *IEEE Trans.*
671 *Microw. Theory Tech.*, vol. 68, no. 9, pp. 3908–3919, Sep. 2020,
672 doi: [10.1109/TMTT.2020.2988688](https://doi.org/10.1109/TMTT.2020.2988688).

673 [19] L. Alonso-González, S. Ver-Hoeye, M. Fernández-García, and
674 F. Las-Heras Andrés, “Three-dimensional fully interlaced woven
675 microstrip-fed substrate integrated waveguide,” *Prog. Electromagn.*
676 *Res.*, vol. 163, pp. 25–38, Aug. 2018, doi: [10.2528/PIER18040207](https://doi.org/10.2528/PIER18040207).

677 [20] L. Alonso-González, S. Ver-Hoeye, M. Fernández-García,
678 and F. Las-Heras Andrés, “Broadband flexible fully textile-
679 integrated bandstop frequency selective surface,” *IEEE Trans.*
680 *Antennas Propag.*, vol. 66, no. 10, pp. 5291–5299, Oct. 2018,
681 doi: [10.1109/TAP.2018.2858141](https://doi.org/10.1109/TAP.2018.2858141).

682 [21] L. Alonso-González, S. Ver-Hoeye, M. Fernández-García, and F. Las-
683 Heras Andrés, “Layer-to-layer angle interlock 3D woven bandstop
684 frequency selective surface,” *Prog. Electromagn. Res.*, vol. 162,
685 pp. 81–94, Jul. 2018, doi: [10.2528/PIER18041707](https://doi.org/10.2528/PIER18041707).

686 [22] L. Alonso-González, S. Ver-Hoeye, M. Fernández-García,
687 Y. Álvarez-López, C. Vázquez-Antuna, and F. Las-Heras Andrés,
688 “Fully textile-integrated microstrip-fed slot antenna for dedicated
689 short-range communications,” *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 66,
690 no. 5, pp. 2262–2270, May 2018, doi: [10.1109/TAP.2018.2814203](https://doi.org/10.1109/TAP.2018.2814203).

691 [23] L. Alonso-González, S. Ver-Hoeye, M. Fernández-García,
692 C. Vázquez-Antuna, and F. Las-Heras Andrés, “On the development
693 of a novel mixed embroidered-wovens slot antenna for wireless
694 applications,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 9476–9489, 2019,
695 doi: [10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2891208](https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2891208).

696 [24] L. Alonso-González, S. Ver-Hoeye, C. Vázquez-Antuna,
697 M. Fernández-García, and F. Las-Heras Andrés, “Multifunctional
698 fully textile-integrated RFID tag to revolutionize the Internet of things
699 in clothing [wireless corner],” *IEEE Antennas Propag. Mag.*, vol. 61,
700 no. 3, pp. 104–110, Jun. 2019, doi: [10.1109/MAP.2019.2907910](https://doi.org/10.1109/MAP.2019.2907910).

701 [25] S. Ver Hoeye, M. Fernández, L. Alonso, C. V. Antuna, P. Ghekiere,
702 and J. A. Casas, “A novel surface-independent textile fully woven
703 UHF RFID tag,” *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 70, no. 11,
704 pp. 10156–10165, Nov. 2022, doi: [10.1109/TAP.2022.3191159](https://doi.org/10.1109/TAP.2022.3191159).

705 [26] M. Fernández, C. Vázquez, and S. Ver Hoeye, “2.4 GHz fully woven
706 textile-integrated circularly polarized rectenna for wireless power
707 transfer applications,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 12, pp. 89836–89844, 2024,
708 doi: [10.1109/ACCESS.2024.3419553](https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2024.3419553).

709 [27] L. Alonso-González, S. Ver-Hoeye, M. Fernández-García,
710 C. Vázquez-Antuna, and F. Las-Heras Andrés, “From threads to
711 smart textile: parametric characterization and electromagnetic analysis
712 of woven structures,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 1486–1501, 2019,
713 doi: [10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2886041](https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2886041).

[28] L. Alonso-González, S. Ver-Hoeye, C. Vázquez-Antuna, 714
M. Fernández-García, and F. Las-Heras Andrés, “On the techniques 715
to develop millimeter-wave textile integrated waveguides using rigid 716
warp threads,” *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Tech.*, vol. 66, no. 2, 717
pp. 751–761, Feb. 2018, doi: [10.1109/TMTT.2017.2777983](https://doi.org/10.1109/TMTT.2017.2777983). 718

[29] H. Yang, X. Liu, Y. Fan, and L. Xiong, “Dual-band textile antenna 719
with dual circular polarizations using polarization rotation AMC for 720
off-body communications,” *IEEE Trans. Antennas Propag.*, vol. 70, 721
no. 6, pp. 4189–4199, Jun. 2022, doi: [10.1109/TAP.2021.3138504](https://doi.org/10.1109/TAP.2021.3138504). 722

MIGUEL FERNÁNDEZ received the First M.Sc. 723
degree in telecommunication engineering, the 724
Second M.Sc. degree in information technology 725
and mobile communications, and the Ph.D. degree 726
from the University of Oviedo, Gijón, Spain, in 727
2006, 2010, and 2010, respectively. 728
From 2006 to 2008, he was a Research Fellow 729
with the Signal Theory and Communications 730
Group, University of Oviedo, where he has been 731
an Associate Professor since September 2008. 732
His main research effort is focused on nonlinear 733
analysis and optimization techniques for the design of oscillator-based 734
circuits, active antennas and frequency multipliers and mixers at the 735
microwave, millimeter/submillimeter-wave, and terahertz frequency bands. 736

CARLOS VÁZQUEZ received the First M.Sc. 737
degree in telecommunication engineering, the 738
Second M.Sc. degree in information technology 739
and mobile communications, and the Ph.D. degree 740
from the University of Oviedo, Gijón, Spain, in 741
2007, 2008, and 2013, respectively. 742
From 2007 to 2012, he was a Graduate Research 743
Assistant from 2012 to 2021. He held different 744
research and technical positions. Since 2021, he 745
has been an Assistant Professor with the Signal 746
Theory and Communications Group, University 747
of Oviedo. His research efforts have extended across different fields, 748
including the nonlinear analysis and optimization techniques for the 749
design of multifunctional oscillator-based circuits, antennas and passive 750
components, such as frequency multipliers and harmonic mixers, at 751
microwave, millimeter/submillimeter-wave, and terahertz frequencies. In the 752
last few years, he has been focused on the design of fully textile-integrated 753
circuits and antennas, suitable for mass production using common processes 754
in the textile industry. 755

SAMUEL VER HOEYE (Member, IEEE) received 756
the M.Sc. degree in electronics engineering from 757
the University of Gent, Gent, Belgium, in 1999, 758
and the Ph.D. degree from the University of 759
Cantabria, Santander, Spain, in 2002. 760
He is currently a Full Professor with 761
the Department of Electrical and Electronic 762
Engineering, University of Oviedo, Gijón, Spain. 763
His main research is focused on the design and 764
analysis of microwave, millimeter wave and THz 765
circuits and systems. Among these are the multi- 766
functional oscillator based circuits and antennas, frequency scanning 767
antennas, graphene based frequency multipliers and mixers, imaging 768
systems, and textile integrated high frequency components. 769